

Original Article

An *in vitro* Evaluation of Anti-Inflammatory and Antimicrobial Activity of Novel Nanocomposite Material Containing Titanium Oxide, Zinc Oxide and Green Tea Extract

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Green tea is an aromatic medicinal beverage obtained from the fresh

leaves and buds of plant *Camellia Sinensis*. It is one of the least processed type of tea which contains many bioactive components. The present study aims to assess the antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity of a novel nanocomposite containing TiO₂, ZnO and green tea extract. In this study antimicrobial activity of the nanocomposite material against common oral pathogens like *S.aureus*, *E. faecalis*, *C.albicans* and *S.mutans* were tested by Agar well diffusion method. Anti-inflammatory effect was tested using egg albumin denaturation assay and bovine serum albumin denaturation assay. All activities yielded excellent results for TiO₂, ZnO nanoparticles, and their nanocomposites. As the concentration increased, the anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activity of the nanoparticles increased. The zone of inhibition was larger in case of *S.aureus* indicating that antibacterial activity was stronger against *S.aureus*. In the future, the novel nanocomposite developed by green synthesis is a promising material for manufacturing antimicrobial agents and bioactive coatings for therapeutic devices. The nanoparticles are incorporated into a wide range of materials to improve the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy and reduce the toxicity. Recent researches on green tea predicts various applications based on the medicinal value to reduce the risk of many modern allopathic medicines.

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Introduction

Nanoparticles are generally described as particles that have sizes ranging from 1 to 100 nm. The polymers that incorporate these nanoparticles are known as nanocomposites. The nanomaterials are classified into organic, inorganic and carbon based nanomaterials. Organic nanomaterials are polymeric and lipid based nanomaterials. Inorganic nanomaterials are metals, metal oxides, ceramics and semiconductor nanomaterials. Carbon based nanomaterials are carbon nano tubes, carbon nano fibres, carbon block, graphene and fullerenes [1]. Due to their improved properties as well as their numerous potential uses, nanoparticle-based

composites have recently attracted a great deal of attention and have been the subject of extensive research especially in the field of biomedicine. Preventing particle aggregation is the lingering difficulty in polymer nanocomposite technology [2].

Green tea is an aromatic medicinal beverage obtained from the fresh leaves and buds of plant *Camellia Sinensis* [3]. Tea plants are native to east Asia especially China. It is obvious that tea has economic and social benefits, and many people consume it every day as a common beverage and as a treatment for a variety of disorders [4]. Since ancient times, green tea has been regarded as a healthy and medicinal beverage, This plant has been advocated as a traditional Chinese medicine for the treatment of fatigue, depression, depressive symptoms, headaches, body aches and pains, digestion, detoxification, and overall life extension [5]. Three main substances found in green tea leaves particularly polyphenolic

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compounds, xanthic bases (caffeine and theophylline), essential oils have an impact on human health. Caffeine primarily affects the central nervous system, promoting alertness, aiding the connection of thoughts, and reducing the feelings of exhaustion [6].

Green tea has a much greater impact on promoting human health and wellbeing than other commonly consumed non-alcoholic beverages due to its contribution to the dietary intake of antioxidant compounds such as catechins and other phytochemicals, certain vitamins like vitamin C, and minerals like Mn, Cr, Se, and Zn. Tea is regarded as a great source of the necessary mineral Mn.^[7] The green synthesis methods for nanocomposite production using green tea offer numerous benefits by utilising the unique properties of ZnO and TiO₂ nanoparticles and minimizes the impact on environment. In the current research the green tea is used as reducing and stabilizing agent for the synthesis of nanoparticles.

The antibacterial activity of extracts of various tea products against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Salmonella sp* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were assessed years back [8]. When the extent of tea fermentation increases, antibacterial activity often decreased. Both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria have been shown to be susceptible to the antibacterial properties of green tea catechins [9]. In contrast to *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Aeromonas hydrophila*, tea extracts suppress enteric pathogens such as *S. aureus*, *S. epidermis*, and *Plesiomonas shigelloides* [8]. ZnO nanoparticles are effective against bacteria and fungi even at low concentrations, making them ideal for thin coating applications [10]. Infections of the skin, mucosa, subcutaneous tissues, and systemic mycoses are all caused by *Candida albicans*. Research has proved the use of plant materials or their extracts as medications to suppress the yeast without damaging the host [11]. Researchers have also compared the antibacterial activity of several spices against yeasts and bacteria to that of antibiotics, which could provide important information on whether extracts can be used in place of or in addition to well-established chemotherapeutic medicines [12].

According to Feris et al. the cytotoxic action of ZnO nanoparticles causes the rupture of lipid bilayers of bacteria and fungi and causing the drainage of the cytoplasmic contents [13]. ZnO nanoparticles has been utilised to synthesis compounds that are effective against a variety of bacterial infections [14]. Significant antibacterial activity of biosynthesized ZnONPs has been studied and demonstrated by Jayaseelan et al [15].

ZnO nanoparticles have been used as a folk cure for inflammatory diseases like fevers, pain, migraines, arthritis and other conditions with anti-inflammatory properties [16]. Terpenoids, flavonoids, and related phenolic and polyphenolic substances, as well as compounds containing sulphur, are clearly categorised in the British Nutrition Foundation report on phytochemicals [17]. An agent's antibacterial action is mostly attributed to two processes, which involve interfering chemically with the production of essential components of bacteria and/or evading the traditional mechanisms of antibacterial resistance [18]. The mechanisms of action can be depicted as, there are numerous targets for antibacterial agents including inhibiting bacterial protein biosynthesis, bacterial cell-wall biosynthesis, bacterial cell membrane destruction, bacterial DNA replication and repair, and inhibition of a metabolic pathway [19].

It is well known that TiO₂NPs have antibacterial properties against both gram positive and gram negative microorganisms. The potential of TiO₂NPs as microbicidal agents is increased by extracts of green tea when combined with their intrinsic antimicrobial and photo catalytic activity [20]. TiO₂NPs' photocatalytic characteristics

enable it to kill germs when exposed to light. The components of the cell membrane may oxidise and eventually be destroyed by reactive oxygen species produced by TiO₂NPs [21,22]. Loss of membrane integrity may result through direct contact with or adsorption of cells onto TiO₂ nanoparticles, even in the absence of light. This is in addition to the photocatalytic activity [23].

Nanoparticles of zinc and Zinc oxide (ZnONPs) is "generally recognised as safe" (U.S. Medicines and health care products regulatory: 21CFR182.8991) and has a low level of toxicity for people. ZnONPs are more biocompatible than TiO₂ and have a strong photocatalytic activity [24]. Due to their high surface to volume ratio and the abrasiveness of their surface, ZnONPs exhibit strong antibacterial activity. Hence zinc oxide is frequently used in the food sector to maintain its colour and prevents rotting [25]. The growth of both gram positive and gram negative bacteria are inhibited by ZnONPs. In the presence of ZnO, gram positive bacteria such *S. aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Enterococcus faecalis* showed a 95% growth suppression [23]. Thus the present study aims at assessing the antimicrobial and anti inflammatory activity of TiO₂, ZnO and nanocomposite containing green tea extract.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of plant extract

100 ml of purified water and 2g of green tea powder were combined and boiled for 10 minutes. After boiling, the extract is filtered through a muslin cloth. After stirring thoroughly it is placed in a heating mantle at 50 to 60 degrees Celsius for 30 minutes. After that the mixture was filtered using Whatmann no.1 filter paper. The filtered extract was stored for synthesis of nanoparticles. Of the 100 ml filtered green tea extract, 60ml of plant extract was used for preparation of nanoparticles. The remaining 30–40 ml of plant extract was used to prepare the concentrate to be used as control.

Preparation of titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles

0.35g (20mM) of titanium oxide was mixed with 70 ml of distilled water. To that 30ml of green tea extract was added and agitated in an orbital shaker for 48 hours at 700- 750 rpm for thorough mixing. The mixture was centrifuged and titanium oxide nanoparticles were synthesised and the pellets were collected and stored for characterisation and biological studies.

0.574g (20 mM) of zinc sulfate was mixed with 70 ml of distilled water. To that 30ml of green tea extract was added and agitated in a magnetic stirrer for 48 hours at 700-750 rpm for thorough mixing on a magnetic stirrer. The mixture was centrifuged and zinc oxide nanoparticle was synthesised and the pellets were collected and stored for characterisation of and research.

Titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanocomposites

The TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticle pellets are collected and dissolved in distilled water. Equal volumes of the solutions are placed separately in a sterile centrifuge and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes. Then the mixture is added to green tea extract. It is kept in hot air oven at 70 degree for 3-4 hrs for drying. After that the powder is collected and stored for further research activities.

Antimicrobial activity

To observe antibacterial efficiency of Specific nanoparticles against the strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. mutans*, and *E. Faecalis* the following method was done. For the study Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) was used to identify the zone of inhibition. Muller-Hinton agar was prepared and sterilised for 45 minutes at 120 lbs. Sterilized

Figure 1: Antimicrobial activity of green tea extract

plates were filled with the medium, which was then left to solidify. The test organisms were swabbed and after that wells were cut with the well cutter. Green tea was placed onto the plates together with titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles in varying concentrations, and the plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The concentration of green tea extract used was 25µl, 50µl, 100 µl. The zone of inhibition was assessed following the incubation period. The presence of antibacterial activity is indicated by the absence of bacterial growth.

Antifungal activity

Agar-well diffusion assays are used to test pathogens such as *C. albicans*. The medium is made using Sabouraud's dextrose agar. Test organisms were swabbed and inoculated into the prepared sterile medium, and then green tea was added to the wells along with titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles in varying concentrations. The plates were incubated for 48–72 hours at 28°C. The zone of inhibition was observed after the incubation period. The presence of antifungal activity is indicated by the absence of fungal growth (figures 1 & 2).

Anti-inflammatory activity

The following protocol, which was modified from the original proposal by Muzushima and Kabayashi, was used to investigate the anti-inflammatory properties of green tea with titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles [26]. Bovine serum albumin (1% aqueous solution), 0.45 ml, and 0.05 ml of green tea containing titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles of varied fixation were combined, and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6.3 using a little amount of 1N hydrochloric acid. These samples were heated to 55°C in a water bath for 30 minutes after being incubated at room temperature for 20 min. After cooling the samples, the absorbance at 660 nm was calculated spectrophotometrically. The benchmark was diclofenac sodium. The control used is DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide is the commonly used co-solvent .

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{\text{Abs}_{\text{control}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{Abs}_{\text{control}}} \times 100$$

Egg albumin denaturation assay

A 5ml solution was created using 2.8ml of freshly manufactured, pH 6.3 phosphate buffered saline and 0.2ml of hen's egg albumin extraction. For green tea, certain amounts of titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles (10 µL, 20 µL, 30 µL, 40 µL, and 50 µL) were synthesised individually. A positive control was employed, which was diclofenac sodium. The mixture were then cooked in a water bath for 15 minutes at 37°C. The samples were then allowed to cool to ambient temperature, and absorbance at 660 nm was measured.

Figure 2: Antimicrobial activity of green tea extract with ZnO and TiO₂

Figure 3: Graphical representation of green tea and ZnO activities

Results

The antibacterial activity of the TiO₂, ZnO and green tea nanocomposite was assessed against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Enterococcus Faecalis* by examining the zone of inhibition. It was compared with standard antibiotic Amoxicirite 100 mg/ml. The zone of inhibition was measured and it was larger in case of *S.aureus* indicating that antibacterial activity was stronger against *S.aureus* followed by *S mutans* and least for *E. Faecalis*. The antifungal activity of the nanocomposite was showing that it is less effective against the fungus *Candida Albicans*. Antibacterial activity of green tea extract was measured at different concentrations and the zone of inhibition was shown as 25 µL (18mm), 50 µL (20mm), 100 µL (25mm) for *S. aureus* (figure 1). Antimicrobial activity of green tea extract and ZnO was measured at different concentrations 25 µL, 50 µL, 100 µL and for *S. aureus*,

it was 25 µL (12 mm), 50 µL (14 mm), 100 µL (18 mm), and for antibiotic (28 mm) Antimicrobial activity was least against *S.mutans* (figures 2 & 3a). In the present study anti-inflammatory activity was assessed by measuring the percentage of inhibition using egg albumin denaturation assay. Percentage of inhibition by green tea extract and ZnO at different concentration was measured as 10 µL (50%), 20 µL (60%), 30 µL (64%), 40 µL (68%), 50 µL (78%) and for the standard drug it was 10 µL (54%), 20 µL (64%), 30 µL (70%), 40 µL (72%), 50 µL (82%). As the concentration increases the % of inhibition also increases (figure 3b). Anti-inflammatory activity of green tea extract and ZnO was measured using bovine serum denaturation assay also. Percentage of inhibition in different concentration was 10 µL (42%), 20 µL (58%), 30 µL (68%), 40 µL (74%), 50 µL (80%). For the standard drug it was 10 µL (48%), 20 µL (60%), 30 µL (72%), 40 µL (80%), 50 µL (84%) (figure 3c).

Figure 4: Antimicrobial and antiinflammatory activities of green tea and TiO₂

Figure 5: Bar graph representations of anti-inflammatory activity-green tea with ZnO and TiO₂ nanocomposite

Antimicrobial activity of Green tea extract and TiO₂ nanoparticles was measured by the zone of inhibition and it was shown that it is stronger against *S. aureus* in 25 µL (12 mm), 50 µL (13 mm), 100 µL (16 mm), and for antibiotic it was (34 mm) (figures 2 & 4a). Anti-inflammatory activity of green tea extract and TiO₂ as assessed using egg albumin denaturation assay is: 10 µL (43%), 20 µL (48%), 30 µL (60%), 40 µL (74%) and 50 µL (80%) and for the standard drug it is 10 µL (55%), 20 µL (64%), 30 µL (70%), 40 µL (72%), 50 µL (80%) (figure 4b). Anti-inflammatory activity of green tea extract and TiO₂ as measured using bovine serum denaturation assay it is 10 µL (50%), 20 µL (52%), 30 µL (60%), 40 µL (62%), 50 µL (80%) (figure 4c). Anti-inflammatory activity of green tea extract, TiO₂ and ZnO nanocomposites as assessed using egg albumin denaturation assay it was 10 µL (52%), 20 µL (61%), 30 µL (64%), 40 µL (68%) and 50 µL (78%) and for standard drug it is 10 µL (54%), 20 µL (64%), 30 µL (68%), 40 µL (70%), 50 µL (80%) (figure 5a). Anti-inflammatory activity of green tea with TiO₂ and ZnO nanocomposite was assessed using bovine serum denaturation assay and is 10 µL (42%), 20 µL (48%), 30 µL (60%), 40 µL (74%) and 50 µL (78%) and for standard drug it is 10 µL (56%), 20 µL (64%), 30 µL (70%), 40 µL (72%), 50 µL (80) (figure 5b).

Discussion

Compared to the beginning of the century, the production and usage of nanoparticle has been improving recently in the present decade. Physio-chemical techniques were previously used to create nanoparticles. Even though it takes less time to create vast amounts of nanoparticles using traditional physical and chemical procedures, the capping agents that are needed to ensure stability require hazardous chemicals, which causes toxicity in the environment. Taking this into account, plant-based green nanotechnology is emerging as a sustainable option due to the efficient use of plant

extracts in the production of nanoparticles.

In the present study, green tea extract with different concentrations was used to test the antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. Fecalis* and *S. mutans*. Zone of inhibition indicated the absence of bacterial growth and diameter of the zones were measured as parameter. It was maximum for *S. aureus* and less for *S. mutans*.

Toda et al in 1989 reported that daily consumption of green tea can kill gram positive *S. aureus* and other harmful bacteria [8]. It has been reported that the green tea contains bioactive components like catechin and polyphenols which is responsible for antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties [27].

As the concentration increased, the anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activity of the nanoparticles increased. The values for the anti-inflammatory properties of zinc oxide nanoparticles were higher than the standard values at all concentrations [28]. The percentage of inhibition was highest in egg albumin denaturation assay. The values for antimicrobial activity of nanocomposite was found to be higher than the standard values at all concentrations of the nanoparticles.

Conclusion

This study has proved that TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles and green tea extract-infused TiO₂ and ZnO nanocomposite materials has strong antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties which was concentration dependant [29]. A high zone of inhibition was found in antimicrobial activity test. The effectiveness and toxicity of the anti-inflammatory activities are also lower. Due to its simplicity and lower cost, the plant extract method appears to be preferable to the microbe method. TiO₂ and ZnO absorbs energy and undergoes photocatalytic degradation producing reactive oxidative species and initiate the degradation of the absorbed chemical species and cell death.

Clinical significance

The unique physical and chemical features of TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles have made these materials useful in the field of modern medicine [30]. Continuing research and advancements have led to the increased usage of these nanoparticles in the field of medicine. In the future, the novel nanocomposite developed by green synthesis is a promising material for manufacturing antimicrobial agents and bioactive coatings for therapeutic devices to reduce the chances of infection and to improve bone mineralization.

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